

PLAY AND GAMES AS MECHANISMS FOR PROMOTING LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme of the didactic-pedagogical activity of playing and games as mechanisms capable of boosting learning possibilities and potentialities. Its scientific relevance lies in the aspect that it discusses, in depth and breadth, the influence of such actions on the cognitive domains. Its social relevance lies in the possibility of responding to family members about the impact of such practices on the formation of children's intelligence and creativity, reflecting on the formation of the adult personality. This is a bibliographical research, based on the pedagogical praxis of the authors and on the thoughts of authors who produced relevant scientific works in this field. For the child, play should represent a free action so that it can provide the child with a journey through the world of make-believe and, thus, in this symbolic game, the child has the freedom to create playful symbols that can function as an inner language, allowing him/her to relive and rethink interesting or impressive events. In order for children to have the opportunity to experience experiences that allow them to fully develop their body, mind and emotions, they must be provided with contexts in which they can run, jump, move with objects, jump over obstacles, climb, organize themselves in groups and fantasize. Fun, leisure and playing are rights guaranteed to all human beings, and when we see an apathetic child, isolated in a corner, without participating in any game, it raises concerns, because the child who does not play is being denied his or her right to childhood, whether by the family or the school. Therefore, it is still necessary to ensure this fundamental right, because through playing, games, toys and games, children discover themselves, fulfill themselves and are able to develop themselves fully.

Keywords: Games. Playfulness. Early childhood educational curriculum. Comprehensive development.

INTRODUCTION

Play is one of the fundamental activities for the development of identity and autonomy in human beings, because while playing, a disentanglement from the real world that surrounds the individual occurs, and they can indulge in their most intrinsic thoughts, creating and recreating reality in their own way. The fact that children, from a very early age, can communicate through gestures, sounds, and later represent a certain role through play, allows them to develop their imagination and, consequently, their creativity.

Through these situations, marked by spontaneity, the child can develop and improve important cognitive and intellectual abilities, such as attention, imitation, memory, and imagination. The socialization process also matures through interaction, use, and experimentation with social rules and roles.

Play should be a free activity so that it can provide the child with a journey through the world of make-believe and, thus, in this symbolic game, they have the freedom to create playful symbols that can function as an inner language, allowing them to relive and rethink interesting or impressive events. When playing make-believe, they seek to imitate, imagine, represent, and communicate in a specific way that one thing can be another, that a person can be a character, that a child can be an object or an animal, that one *make-believe place* is another. Play is, therefore, a space in which one can observe the coordination of the child's previous experiences and what the manipulated objects suggest or provoke in the present moment.

By repeating what they already know, using their mnemonic capacity, children utilize their prior knowledge, expanding and transforming it through the creation of a new imaginary situation. Play, therefore, constitutes an internal activity of the child, based on the development of imagination and the interpretation of reality, without being illusion or falsehood. In this way, they also become the author of their roles, choosing, elaborating, and putting into practice their fantasies and knowledge, as well as their unique and particular interpretation of the world in which they are immersed. Without adult intervention, they can think and solve problems freely, unburdened by the situational pressures of immediate reality.

At other times, play should be coordinated through activities that allow interaction with the group and aim at full physical and motor development. To pedagogically address these two moments, it is necessary to consider what types of toys and/or games can be indicated and used, respecting the physical conditions and age of each child.

Just as play is important, games should be conceived, developed, and implemented in schools considering pedagogical and didactic parameters, in order to achieve the objectives of

cognitive and intellectual development of students. It must always be clarified that games and play do not replace formal learning experiences; both are complementary, and *insights are expected* to arise from situations previously experienced in the classroom.

Mechanisms for the Development of Games and Play Activities

In schools, certain equipment and spaces considered playful—understanding this concept to encompass all physical and spatial elements aimed, in some way, at promoting learning—are indispensable resources for the child's development in all its aspects, including, among others:

- a) *Equipment*: those traditionally found in courtyards and squares: swings, slides, bars, merry-go-rounds, etc.;
- b) *Sand*: including also soil, pebbles, sticks, etc.;
- c) *Cozy corners*: these are secluded spaces where children seek to be alone or with their favorite companions. For example: shelter in vegetation, holes in buildings, etc.;
- d) *Elevations*: This includes ramps, stairs, benches, walls, and all objects that allow children to use them to climb or scale (excluding slides). *Body*: This involves using one's own body to play: running, jumping, singing, talking, fighting, etc.

Other resources that are sometimes overlooked are the types of play that can be suggested or allowed for the child, such as:

- *Physical activity*: involves games such as running, climbing, swinging, playing ball, tag, etc.;
- *Constructive*: games that involve building something, using, for example, sand, tires, or objects in general;
- *Symbolic*: involves make-believe;
- *Others*: singing, shouting, etc.

Understanding that, in some early childhood education schools, both space and budget are often limited, teachers should think about equipment that can be used in a wide variety of situations and ways. In the area of dramatic play, equipment with fewer details can be used more flexibly, as children's imaginations can turn a simple box into a rocket or a train car.

In order for children to have opportunities to engage in experiences that allow them to fully develop their bodies, thoughts, and emotions, contexts must be provided in which they can run, jump, move with objects, leap over obstacles, climb, organize themselves into groups,

fantasize, etc. Therefore, teachers of preschool children should pay special attention to the outdoor spaces of their preschool, equipping them with materials that allow children to carry out key experiences within this domain.

Early childhood education professionals should also observe, during this specific period of child development, the importance of appropriating body image. Acquiring awareness of the limits of one's own body is an important aspect in the development of the process of differentiating *oneself* from *others* and in the construction of identity.

Through exploration, physical contact with others, and observation of those around them, children learn about the world, about themselves, and communicate through body language. In this way, the resources provided by the school become an integral part of the resources offered: a mirror that allows the child to see themselves in their entirety, and a treasure chest of clothes and accessories with which they can visualize themselves in various ways. This play, according to Piaget, represents "a language of gestures, movements, and mimicry, as much as a language of words" (Piaget, n.d., *cited in* Lopes, n.d., p. 48).

Play and games are part of every child's life, at any time and place. They are effective tools for human development, as they foster imagination, creativity, socialization, expression, discussion, reciprocity, problem-solving skills, and cooperative behaviors.

A preschool that aims to work with children through a process of concrete knowledge construction must take into account that play and games are part of their daily lives, serving as enjoyable learning spaces that should be present in their routine. Sometimes, games and play are related to mathematics, language, science, and the arts, considering that it is through play that children interact with facts and seek to understand them through unconscious and preconscious internalization.

Once this mechanism is brought to light by the child herself, she begins to create proposals and conditions for psychological arrangements that are gradually externalized through the language she masters, using the vocabulary at her disposal as a way to explain her actions and transformations. It is at this point that play becomes capable of providing significant aspects of cognitive and intellectual development, especially if an adult intervenes and assists her in her creations and interpretations of reality.

As the child becomes aware of the game and begins to interpret all of reality by reducing it to a game, this cannot be understood as a pejorative reduction of life, existence, and the phenomena that compose them, but rather as the way they have found to keep things within their phenomenological field of apprehension and processing capacity. This can be explained as a way that *Physis (the human body)* has found to compensate humankind for the evolutionary

process imposed upon them, which deprived them of the conditions to understand nature and its nuances. Thus, unable, due to their cognitive immaturity, to ascend to the level of understanding nature, their action is to bring it to their level, transforming it into an element they can decipher, making use of the knowledge they possess up to that moment.

Under no circumstances does the child distort reality by doing this; they adapt it to their epistemic scope and thus make their inferences, explaining facts and phenomena, all under a very rigorous veil of scientificity. The aspect of play that is presented to adults is seen only by them, which reveals that the children's world is treated in a bizarre way, interpreted according to the whims of the moment and ignorance about its workings. From this approach to an interpretation of children's thinking, what characterizes play and games in their world, clarifying that it is not a matter of understanding them; but how they categorize them, what epistemological dimension is attributed to them, and how will this be represented in adolescence and adulthood by the same individual, now in another phase of their existence?

Nietzsche (1844-1900) asserts that this feeling persists in human beings *ad aeternum* and that every adult hides within themselves a child who longs to play. Taking this statement from the philosopher, one can conclude that the human tendency to reduce all *or part of the reality that surrounds them* to the realm of comprehensibility is an ontogenetic inheritance, a product of childhood play. The extent to which all this is assimilated by human thought and processed as a determining factor in personality is what challenges knowledge and, perhaps, could clarify why children who enjoyed the freedom to expand their worlds through supposed play become adults more capable of analyzing, interpreting, and synthesizing social and natural phenomena with greater insight, transparency, and autonomy.

One possible explanation for this phenomenon is that when children are carried away by the lightness of play and games, in the absence of ridiculous rules imposed by adults who believe themselves to be educators and who claim to be concerned with the formation of the child's character, and where the group of participants themselves make decisions about the mechanisms for adjusting and balancing the situations presented, they begin to understand that the rules they don't understand and hate in the adult world are also part of their childhood spaces, and that they can even be expelled or punished if they don't respect the rules established for that seemingly childish and perhaps innocent situation.

Children's behavior is strongly determined by the characteristics of the concrete situations in which they find themselves. As children acquire language, they become capable of using symbolic representation. Therefore, they are able to free their psychological functioning from the concrete elements present in the current moment. It is important to

emphasize the importance of real situations and the fusion that young children make between perceived elements and their meaning. They are unable to operate with a meaning that contradicts the present perceptual information, because in a situation like play, the child is led to act in an imaginary world, in which the situation is defined by the meaning established by the game and not by the real elements present around them.

Play and games go far beyond what is expected in the educational spectrum, and the great interest lies in discovering how to use them for pedagogical purposes without reducing them to just that. Children tend to resist what is imposed on them as a formal objective and which impedes, in part or in whole, their natural freedom of expression. In this sense, the intervention of an adult, teacher or not, must be planned well in advance so that it is not rejected by the child, who may understand such action as a violation of their particular world, in which there is no space for anyone else but themselves.

This belief that children learn to socialize through play and games is just that, a belief; what they create are their own strict rules, with no right to appeal, and they impose them on everyone, not allowing them to be disregarded under penalty of exclusion for the transgressor. Over time, when analyzing children's activities, considered innocent, one realizes that the doctrines they elaborate are much more severe and cold than those that exist in the adult world, where there is the possibility of resorting to attempts at explanations and justifications in order to escape punishment.

Both playful situations merely seek to reduce the adult world, incomprehensible to the child, to their level of cognitive understanding; however, they do not bring with them the rules of this world. It seems like a complex and difficult situation to understand; but, literally, they *create* a space for action and reaction in which everything they plan is executed to the letter, without this hindering their learning experience. After this argument, the approximation is that it is not about learning what is done in the adult world, which does not interest them; but about reinforcing what they already have as intrinsic value, a product of the influence of their socio-cultural formation.

If a child gives *meaning* to the world around them through play and games, what signifier do they take as a symbolic object? Where do they get the determinations they impose on others with such rigor and even with violent undertones? Studies and research on the development of play and games and their respective meanings provide a closer understanding of how children discover the world through these activities and interpret it. It is always necessary to clarify that, before discovering the meaning of actions considered playful by

children, one must try to understand what they symbolize for them, in the general and particular context; because...

At the beginning of preschool age, when desires arise that cannot be immediately satisfied or forgotten, and the characteristic of the preceding stage—a tendency toward the immediate satisfaction of these desires—remains, the child's behavior changes. To resolve this tension, the preschool child engages in an illusory and imaginary world where unrealizable desires can be fulfilled, and this world is what we call play (Vygotsky, 2000 *apud* Lopes, n.d., p. 48).

This explanation by Vygotsky, if taken hastily, leaves the impression that the child is using games and play as compensation for weakness demonstrated at an earlier age; however, it is not age, *per se*, that determines the potential of a human being, but rather a phase, which encompasses a specific age range, and within each of these, there are very unique feelings and desires, each requiring a contextual redundancy of the world until it becomes an object of self-mastery. Using their imagination, the child overcomes barriers. Depending on the role they play, the influence of their feelings is noticeable: manifestations of fear, love, anxiety, aggression, etc. And, often, it is through play that they manage to internally process these emotions.

The thing is, imagination is too abstract a feeling for a still immature brain; therefore, what the child does is subject an uncontrollable world to their design by reducing it to a model they can control. Endowed with a capacity for concrete intelligence, everything they create or destroy in their mind is the result of a ruthless adjustment to their cognitive and intellectual level, nothing beyond that; nothing less than that.

Therefore, how can we interpret children's games and play, and how can we reproduce them within a pedagogical framework that is as faithful as possible to the psychic world of children? The first contribution is that it is not known how these activities motivate and influence thought, transforming it in a way that improves and strategically refines it for a greater understanding and synthesis of reality. One thing that is observed is that the more freedom they are given in carrying out their playful activities, games, and play, the more capable they are of solving highly complex problems and abstracting; However, to categorically state what they learned and why they did it is to exaggerate the degree of didactic incoherence and to risk ridicule, because even if long-term studies are conducted in which it is possible to prove the learning of certain curricular content through the didactic use of games and play for recreational purposes, each human being is unique and, at most, this could be proof that it worked with a

certain group of students at a certain time; it can never be used as a given and defined end, becoming a research of *social representation* .

The main strategy for understanding and comprehending play and games in the development of children's cognitive and intellectual abilities is through observation and the results in the development of thought, motor skills, and overall performance. If, on the one hand, it is necessary to understand the contemporary world and its great universalizing influence, on the other hand, children's culture constitutes an indispensable element for the survival of adult culture itself.

Children cannot be portrayed as beings devoid of creativity, as has sometimes been suggested. There is no doubt that television heroes will be transformed when they come to inhabit children's imaginations. Industrial toys will be explored by children and, if they provide some material for fantasy, they will survive; otherwise, they will be abandoned at the bottom of the toy box.

Playful activities are extremely important for the expression of personality and the cognitive development of children. Through play, children gradually acquire self-confidence, knowledge of their possibilities, autonomy, and their relationship with the world. Besides being an imaginary situation, play is also an activity governed by rules. It is precisely the rules of the game that cause the child to behave in a more advanced way than is usual for their age. What is natural and goes unnoticed in real life becomes a rule in play and helps the child understand the particular universe of the various roles they play.

Both through the creation of imaginary situations and the definition of specific rules, play creates a zone of proximal development for the child. In play, the child behaves in a more advanced way than in real-life activities and also learns to separate object and meaning. Although a superficial examination may suggest that play has little resemblance to more complex psychological activities of human beings, a deeper analysis reveals that actions in play are subordinated to the meanings of objects, clearly contributing to the development of the child's intellect; since,

In group play, social relationships are reproduced in the relationships between children. Regulated by implicit rules of behavior, these relationships are an important precondition for children to gradually become aware of the existence of rules in play. It is on this basis that games with rules (such as hopscotch, sports, cards) emerge (Fontana; Cruz, 1997, p. 135).

According to Piaget (1896-1980), these games are characterized by the pre-determination of social rules which, from the moment children understand existence in a world

where the presence of others marks a decisive space, lead them to respect the rules and also create their own, as a way of asserting themselves as human beings. If, in a previous phase, the child played alone, freely manipulating objects, representing roles; in short, playing *make-believe games*, this new phase inaugurates dependence on the participation of others, submission to rules that, established *a priori*, will permeate the game and demand control of behavior. To play hopscotch, each participant must wait their turn, respect the drawn limits, alternate jumping with one foot and both feet, and the participant who does not respect these rules will be eliminated. Thus, the pleasure of play ceases to be concentrated on the doing and turns to the conscious realization of the purpose that justifies the actions. In the case of a race, the children must start together; But the goal is to achieve the objective, which is to arrive first.

Choosing to intervene in children's development, helping them become creative, cooperative, and more humane, is a challenge that will guarantee not only the right to play, recreating the world around them, but also a future harmonious relationship between individuals. Children express themselves through their movements, posture, gestures, gaze, face, and walk. Therefore, the child's body is speech, it is expression. These elements define the importance of the body's involvement in play and games in early childhood education institutions, not in the sense of mechanical motor exercise techniques, but in bodily experiences as a revealing instance of being and existence, where movement is a form of language capable of synthesizing emotions and feelings.

It is essential to recognize that, once the relevant role of games and play in child development is understood, the teacher must find or prepare the space where the structuring of the proposed mechanisms occurs, perceiving the child as an active being, with the possibility of becoming a builder of their own development. Starting from the principle that play represents, for the child, the reduction of the macro universe to their micro universe, with the purpose not of understanding it, but of mastering it, it follows that, in doing so, they discover themselves capable of making it less obscure; broader and more appropriate to what they think about it and, once this becomes possible, they begin to elaborate their theories in response to their doubts and questions. Huguet (n.d.) argues that the integral development of the child during the Early Childhood Education stage is concentrated in three major areas of knowledge, namely:

- *Motor area* – includes everything related to the human body's ability to move, both as a whole and in its segments;
- *Cognitive area* – addresses the abilities that allow one to understand the world, at different ages, and to act in it, through the use of language or by solving problematic situations that arise. Even so, it is necessary to refer to the abilities

that a child of this age has to create or communicate through the use of all languages (verbal, artistic, etc.);

- *Affective area* – encompasses aspects related to the possibilities of feeling good about oneself (personal balance), which allows one to confront new situations and people (interpersonal relationship) and to establish increasingly detached, distant relationships, as well as to act in the world around them (social action and insertion) (Huguet, n.d. *apud* Lopes, n.d., p. 31).

Children learn a great deal through play; their games reveal rules and knowledge, dynamize concepts, and enhance experiences. Games and play allow learning to occur without trauma or mechanization, because through play and games, children interact directly with knowledge and construct it according to their possibilities and reality. According to Vygotsky (1998), when playing, children create an imaginary situation where rules always exist, simply because from the moment an imaginary situation exists, it has rules of behavior that are represented in the play.

Thus, the essence of play is the possibility for the child to symbolically express motivations, plans, and intentions, creating a new relationship between real situations and - fulfilling their own needs. It is a specific activity of childhood, in which the child recreates reality using symbolic systems. It is a creative human activity in which imagination, fantasy, and reality interact to produce new possibilities for interpretation, expression, and action by children, as well as new ways of building social relationships with other individuals, both children and adults.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In early childhood education, there are activities within the spectrum of playfulness, which are recognized as an important resource for the learning process. Play in a school setting serves to transmit knowledge to children, such as reading, writing, mathematical problem-solving skills, and information in the areas of history, geography, and science. Unfortunately, play and games are often not used as tools to enhance students' learning capacity. Play is considered synonymous with distraction and, therefore, is not used as a valuable procedure for this purpose.

Play and games should be part of the educational curriculum in the classroom, as it is understood that play contributes to the development of various cognitive aspects that induce learning processes. Therefore, recreation can be a great contributor to the development and deepening of classroom content commonly worked on with children attending daycare and preschool.

It is known that fun, leisure, and play are rights guaranteed to every human being, and when one sees a child apathetic, isolated in a corner, not participating in any games, it raises concerns, because a child who does not play is having their right to childhood denied, whether by family or school. Therefore, it is still necessary to ensure this fundamental right, because through play, games, toys, and play, the child discovers themselves, fulfills themselves, and is able to develop holistically.

Legal documents clearly state that education and care must go hand in hand, implying a pedagogical practice based on an integrated vision of child development, respecting the unique characteristics of each child and providing meaningful and enjoyable learning opportunities. Understanding this from a legal, pedagogical, and didactic perspective, one gains a proper understanding of the importance of play in a child's school life; therefore, care and play situations should be provided, organized according to children's characteristics, in order to promote development and learning through experiences that lead to knowledge and a subsequent capacity for interpreting phenomena.

Regarding the space for play, it can be said that this has become complicated, since children no longer have the same freedom on the streets as before, due to the risks and dangers. However, some children still have certain privileges such as going to parks and clubs. But, also considering those who do not enjoy the same privilege, what can be done to provide a pleasant environment for these children, so that they can make contact with an intrapsychic space where they can have fun with their discoveries?

Therefore, it cannot be forgotten that playing in the street is a time to interact with other children, since space at home is often limited. To this end, this enjoyable play should be introduced into the school curriculum, as the playful interpretation of games and playfulness is more likely to occur at school. On the other hand, with homes becoming increasingly cramped and adults preoccupied with their daily lives, middle-class children often lack space to play and should not disrupt the household routine with their toys.

Another relevant point to highlight is the fact that television occupies a significant space for most children. The moment a child begins to awaken to the world, they are precisely in front of a television. In this way, they discover other forms of pleasure, which causes games and activities that require broad movements and in-depth investigations to be sidelined. As a result, the child begins to lose interest in playfulness and science, and starts to focus on new issues in their daily lives that require little or no intellectual activity, since everything is already presented in its colorful and predetermined form within a state of apparent, harmonious perfection.

As one might expect, time dedicated to play at school remains almost impossible, and indeed, scarce. There are various justifications for this "lack of time." The most common seems to be: " *We need to cover a lot of material* " and, " *Therefore, there's no time left, or we don't have time to waste* ."

It is understood, therefore, that when a child is at school, they should be offered a wide variety of situations that provide systematic or occasional individual experiences necessary for their integral development, in order to rekindle their enjoyment and interest in play. Thus, a playful-pedagogical space for consolidating learning can be created in the classroom, where one learns by playing and learns by playing. The emphasis is on transforming knowledge *into action*, and thus providing time and space for play in school education.

Based on this study, it is also necessary to emphasize that play is a source of stimulation that enables children's cognitive, socio-interactive, affective, and linguistic development. In this sense, it is important to encourage children to play. Teachers should offer toys, time, and adequate and sufficient space for children to play, considering the classroom as the ideal space where three perspectives – caring, educating, and playing – meet, and this meeting must be such that the result is a happy child, endowed with creative thinking and autonomy.

It is suggested that schools reflect on the perception of physical space as a socializing instrument and provider of meaningful learning for children. Considering the diverse interests of society, family, and especially the child, and recognizing the impact that physical space has on individual actions, the teacher can organize this environment to meet their real needs. However, it is important to understand what space is available and what is needed. Recognizing existing limitations is a good way to rethink proposed activities and what games and play can be carried out individually, in groups, or even with a view to pedagogical support. It is also necessary to consider the scarcity of equipment, furniture, and material resources, or, when available, whether they are used appropriately by professionals. The space should also promote a sense of security and confidence. It should be stimulating in various forms of expression: graphic, motor, musical, etc., and allow for child-to-child, child-to-adult, and child-to-object interaction. In this way, it will cater to the well-being of children, giving them opportunities for social contact, privacy for physical, cognitive, and emotional growth, and the autonomous construction of their identity.

For these guarantees to be effective, it is not necessary to exclude or break down the structures of existing early childhood education schools. It is enough to understand how to use the spaces, starting from the child's basic needs. In short, the organized spaces should aim for

the full experience of childhood, based on the principles of early childhood education, guided by a sound curriculum proposal.

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